

Solvent Sensitized Dye Interaction Technique for End Group Analysis of Acrylonitrile Polymers : Part I—Development of the Method

C. KANJILAL, B. C. MITRA, S. R. PALIT and A. K. BANTHIA

Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science,
Jadavpur, Calcutta-700 032

Manuscript received 17 November 1976, revised 6 October 1977, accepted 14 February 1978

For the detection and estimation of carboxyl end groups in polyacrylonitrile polymers (ca. 10^{-5} mole/l) for which the usual dye methods are not applicable due to poor solubility of the polymer, a "solvent sensitized dye interaction technique (SSDIT)" has been successfully developed. For routine detection and exact quantitative analysis methylene blue MT dye reagent is used and a suitable calibration curve has been prepared with cyanoacetic acid and a carboxyl end model polyacrylonitrile polymers. Partially N-alkylated triphenyl methane dye also produces dye reagent of similar acid sensitivity whereas fully alkylated dyes (both of thiazine and triphenyl methane classes) produce insensitive or, less sensitive dye reagents.

THE elegant dye techniques, introduced by one of the authors¹⁻³, viz. the dye partition technique¹, the dye interaction technique² and the relatively recently introduced reverse dye partition technique³, have all been widely applied for the identification of various types of end groups incorporated anionically and cationically in different vinyl polymers. Of these, the former two proved to be useful for low dielectric (water-insoluble) benzene-or, chloroform-soluble polymers whereas the last technique was utilized for water-soluble polymers. Neither the dye partition method nor the dye interaction method however can be applied for end group analysis for polymers such as polyacrylonitriles which are soluble only in water-soluble high dielectric solvents such as N,N-dimethylformamide, dimethyl sulfoxide, hexamethyl phosphoramide, etc. However, Palit and Ghosh^{4,5} suggested the use of such solvents to remove the above limitation and the present paper reports such a successful solvent sensitization of the Dye interaction technique (SSDIT) to enable determination of -COOH groups in polyacrylonitrile.

Experimental

Acrylonitrile (ACN) was purified by distillation under reduced pressure.

N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF) was treated twice with phosphorous pentoxide for 5-6 hours followed by washing with solid caustic potash. It was subsequently filtered and distilled under reduced pressure. Just before use it was redistilled. Benzene was purified by successive washing with concentrated sulfuric acid, caustic soda solution and distilled water. It was then dried over fused calcium chloride, distilled and stored over sodium metal. All other solvents were purified by the usual methods and distilled before use.

Methylene blue MT (E. Merck), methylene blue (E. Merck), methyl violet (B.D.H.) and crystal violet (B.D.H.) were thrice crystallized.

The cyanoacetic acid used for calibration was prepared from reagent grade ethyl cyanoacetate by the following procedure. The ester was mixed with two parts of water and a few drops of nitric acid and heated at 60° until a homogeneous solution was obtained from which cyanoacetic acid crystals were obtained on evaporation. It was then purified by recrystallization from a mixture of ether and chloroform.

Polyacrylonitrile (PACN) samples bearing carboxyl end group were prepared as follows: (1) by aqueous polymerization technique using KMnO_4 -oxalic acid redox initiating system; (2) by thermal polymerization using 4,4'-azobis-4-cyanopentanoic acid as initiator. The carboxyl content of these samples was determined by titration^{6,7} in DMF with aqueous caustic potash ($\sim N/20$) using phenolphthalein as indicator.

The viscosity average molecular weight (\bar{M}_v) of the polymer (PACN-unfractionated) was obtained viscometrically using the equation⁸

$$[\eta] = 3.92 \times 10^{-4} \bar{M}_v^{0.75} \text{ in DMF, } 25^\circ \quad (1)$$

Preparation of the Dye Reagent: The benzene extract of the dye commonly called the dye reagent, was obtained by immediate extraction from an approximately 0.4 wt. % aqueous caustic soda solution of methylene blue MT (8-10 mg in 5 ml) with 100 ml. of thiophene free pure benzene. This red coloured dye extract was then stored over solid caustic soda in dark. Dye reagent

for other dyes used in the present study was prepared similarly.

Procedure for acid end group analysis in polyacrylonitriles using solvent sensitized dye interaction technique (SSDIT) :

A solution of purified polymer of a known concentration in DMF (approximately 4-10 mg in 3 ml.) was mixed with the properly diluted dye reagent (2 ml.) in a well stoppered test tube. A change in colour of the dye reagent from red to blue in the homogeneous mixed solvent medium indicated the presence of anionic end groups in the polymer. The intensity of the blank colour and the developed colour was measured at 650 nm in a Hilger spekker absorptiometer in stoppered 1 cm. cells. The optical density of the blank dye in the solvent mixture DMF-benzene (3 : 2 parts by volume) was maintained at 0.08 at 650 nm. Optical density higher than this indicated the presence of acidic end groups in the polymer. An estimate of the acidic end group content of the polymer was then obtained by comparison with the standard calibration curve using the following equation :

$$\text{No. of end groups per polymer molecule} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Molarity of the macroacid} \\ \text{solution (from calibration} \\ \text{curve)} \times \text{Molecular weight} \\ \text{of the polymer weight of the} \\ \text{polymer per litre of the} \\ \text{solution} \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

Results and Discussion

The underlying principle of SSDIT is similar to that of the existing dye interaction technique^{2,4,5} for the analysis of acid end groups in polymers, except using DMF as a solubilizer and sensitizer. It may be mentioned that PACN by itself has no affinity for the

Fig. 1. Spectra of the Dye Reagent in Different Solvent Mixtures.

- I. Methylene Blue MT Dye Extract in Benzene.
- II. Dye Extract in Benzene-Chloroform (2 : 3 v/v) mixture.
- III. Dye Extract in Benzene-Acetone (2 : 3 v/v) mixture.
- IV. Dye Extract in Benzene-DMSO (2 : 3 v/v) mixture.
- V. Dye Extract in Benzene-DMF (2 : 3 v/v) mixture.

dye but PACN with carboxyl groups strongly adsorb the dye from the dye reagent with colour change (red to blue) and this polymer-bound dye is easily extracted out by alcohol but not at all by benzene ; of course, the whole polymer plus dye dissolves in DMF.

(A) Choice of solvent-mixture used for SSDIT

The spectra of the methylene blue MT dye reagent in benzene as well as in different solvent mixtures with benzene as the common component (2 parts by volume) and DMF, DMSO, acetone, and chloroform separately as the other component (3 parts by volume) show a maxima at 540 nm (Fig. 1). Interaction with acid functional groups present either in simple organic compounds like formic acid or, polymers (polyacrylonitrile) causes a special shift from red to blue showing a maxima at 650 nm (Fig. 2). It is also evident from this study that a better sensitivity is offered for solvent mixtures benzene-DMF, or benzene-DMSO over benzene or, other solvent mixtures tried without affecting the dye reagent characteristics. For further study benzene-DMF mixture was used.

Fig. 2. Spectra of the Developed Colour of the Dye Reagent in Different Solvent Mixtures.

- I. Dye Extract in Benzene+Formic acid^a.
 - II. Dye Extract in Benzene-CHCl₃ (2 : 3 v/v)+Formic acid^a.
 - III. Dye Extract in Benzene-Acetone (2 : 3 v/v)+Formic acid^a.
 - IV. Dye Extract in Benzene-DMF (2 : 3 v/v)+Formic acid^a.
 - V. Dye Extract in Benzene-DMSO (2 : 3 v/v)+Formic acid^a.
 - VI. Dye Extract in Benzene+PACN with Carboxyl Group in DMF^b (Benzene : DMF=2 : 3 v/v).
 - VII. Dye Extract in Benzene+PACN with Carboxyl Group in DMSO^b (Benzene : DMSO=2 : 3 v/v).
- a. [HCOOH]— 2.0×10^{-3} mole/l.
b. [PACN-COOH]— 5.0×10^{-5} mole/l.

(B) Search for a suitable calibration standard

The success of this dye technique would generally depend on the proper choice of a suitable material as reference for calibration. Cyanoacetic acid offered the best sensitivity even comparable to polyacrylonitrile sample bearing known amount of carboxylic end groups. Within the concentration range (1×10^{-5} - 7×10^{-5} mole/l) studied the sensitivity decreases in the following order: carboxyl bearing PACN \approx cyanoacetic acid > nitrobenzoic acid > phenol acetic acid > stearic acid > benzoic acid.

Cyanoacetic acid and PACN samples having known amounts of carboxylic end group are thus used as reference materials for calibration and exhibit the same identical curve, when optical density values of the different test solutions are plotted against their respective concentrations in mole/litre.

(C) Verification of the accuracy of the calibration curve

Determination of the number average molecular weight from intrinsic viscosity on one hand and from the above calibration curve by end group estimation (based on the assumption of the end group content per polymer molecule) on the other hand their mutual comparison can provide a possible clue for verification. For this purpose, PACN samples containing carboxyl end group at one end only was prepared with 4,4'-azobis-4-cyanopentanoic acid in DMF at 60° using FeCl₃ as chain terminator. Under these conditions all the polymer chains were expected to be terminated by FeCl₃ and the resultant polymer will have carboxyl group at one end only^{6,9}. The number of average molecular weight can then be easily calculated from the following equation :

$$\text{Number average molecular weight} = \frac{x}{\text{Molarity of the macroacid solution}} \quad (3)$$

where x is the percentage strength of the macroacid solution. In turn, corresponding molarity of the macro-

acid solution can be obtained directly by SSDIT. It is evident from Table-1 that the number average molecular weight \bar{M}_n of the model samples obtained by SSDIT as well as viscometrically compare reasonably well within experimental error. This proves the suitability of the present SSDIT for the estimation of acid end group in polyacrylonitrile polymer.

(D) Suitability of other basic dyes for SSDIT

Possibility of using other basic dyes for SSDIT has also been investigated. Of the four dyes chosen for the

Fig. 3. Plot of Optical Density vs. Concentration of Carboxyl Groups in a Standard PACN and Cyanoacetic Acid to prepare a Calibration Curve.

- Calibration Curve using Cyanoacetic Acid.
- Calibration Curve using PACN.

purpose, methylene blue MT and methylene blue are of thiazine type whereas methyl violet and crystal violet represent the triphenylmethane class. It has been

TABLE 1—VERIFICATION OF THE CALIBRATION CURVE WITH STANDARD PACN SAMPLES

Concn. of the Azo-acid mole/l $\times 10^4$	Concn. of FeCl ₃ mole/l $\times 10^3$	[η] dl/g	Concn. of PACN %	O.D. at 650 nm	Molecular weights	
					Calc. from the observed O. D 10^{-4}	Calc. from [η] 10^{-4}
2.18	1.03	2.36	0.198	0.229	10.92	10.96
2.18	1.85	2.19	0.210	0.242	10.80	9.908
1.38	1.78	2.89	0.204	0.199	14.10	14.35

Fig. 4. Plot of Optical Density vs. Concentration of Carboxyl Group in PACN with Different Dye Reagents.

- I. Calibration with Methyl Violet.
- II. Calibration with Methylene Blue.
- III. Calibration with Crystal Violet.

observed (Figs. 3 and 4) that though methylene blue MT is quite sensitive for our purpose ordinary methylene blue does not yield a sensitive dye reagent. Similarly methyl violet yields a dye reagent which is almost as sensitive as methylene blue MT but crystal violet, the fully alkylated product is rather insensitive.

This appears to be due to the fact that the fully alkylated dyes are constitutionally incapable of forming the anhydrobase^{4,6}. The calibration can be done by cyanoacetic acid.

(E) Limitation of SSDIT

All salts are quite insoluble in benzene and consequently are mostly insensitive to dyes. However, mercuric salts and quaternary salts are sufficiently soluble in benzene and produce strong colour reaction with dye reagent. Some iodides and thiocyanates produce weak colour reaction and therefore care should be taken to purify the polymer.

References

1. S. R. PALIT, *Makromol. Chem.*, 1959, 36, 89; 1960, 38, 96.
2. S. R. PALIT, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1960, 1531; *Anal. Chem.*, 1961, 33, 1441.
3. S. MUKHOPADHYAY, B. C. MITRA and S. R. PALIT, *J. Poly. Sci., A-1*, 1969, 7, 2442.
4. S. R. PALIT and P. GHOSH, *Microchem. Tech.*, 1961, 2, 663.
5. P. GHOSH and S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 41, 567.
6. C. H. BAMFORD, A. D. JENKINS and R. HOHNSTON, *Proc. Roy. Soc., (London)*, 1957, A239, 214.
7. G. S. MISRA and V. P. GUPTA, *Makromol. Chem.*, 1964, 71, 110.
8. P. F. ONYAN, *J. Poly. Sci.*, 1956, 22, 13.
9. B. M. MANDAL, D. Phil., Thesis, Calcutta University, 1967.